

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 857612.

“Integration of Geodetic and imAging TechIques for monitoring and modelling the Earth's surface deFoRmations and Seismic risk – GATHERS”

1st GATHERS Summer school – 19th-24th September 2022, UWPr, Wrocław and Rybnik, Poland

PROGRAM

	Monday 19 September 2022	Tuesday 20 September 2022	Wednesday 21 September 2022	Thursday 22 September 2022	Friday 23 September 2022	Saturday 24 September 2022
	Wrocław	Wrocław	Wrocław / Rybnik	Rybnik	Rybnik	Rybnik / Wrocław
09:00-10:30	09:00 - 09:30 Registration (building C2) Opening session (room II G)	InSAR tutorial (room 102 G)	LiDAR tutorial (room 102 G)	GNSS theory	GNSS tutorial	Travel to Wrocław (departire at 8:30)
10:30-11:00	Photo & coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	
11:00-12:30	InSAR theory (room II G)	LiDAR theory (room II G)	Soft skills trainings (room 202 G)	GNSS theory	GNSS tutorial	
12:30-14:00	LUNCH	LUNCH	LUNCH	LUNCH	LUNCH	
14:00-15:30	InSAR theory (room II G)	LiDAR theory (room II G)	Soft skills trainings (room 202 G)	Field measurements (GNSS)	Field measurements (UAV)	
15:30-16:00	Coffee break	Coffee break	Travel to Rybnik (departure at 15:45)	Coffee break	Coffee break	
16:00-18:00	InSAR tutorial (room 102 G)	LiDAR tutorial (room 102 G)		Workshop	Museum visit	
18:30-20:30	Welcome event (building A2)	City guided tour (departure at 18:15)		Gala dinner	School results and diploma ceremony	

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UPWr Campus and C2 – C1 building plan

